

THE REASONS FOR THE ORIGIN OF CORRUPTION CRIMES, THE CONDITIONS THAT ALLOW THEM, AS WELL AS THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF COOPERATION IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PREVENTION

Khazratov Tolkin Nuritdinovich

Acting commander of the detachment of the educational-part of the Academy of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, major

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Annotation: *Through this article, you can learn about the causes of corruption-related crimes and the conditions that allow them, as well as the activities of the Prevention of this crime, the functions of the public and state bodies in the fight against corruption crime, the correct Organization of cooperation, modern methods and techniques of combating this crime, the advantages of introducing foreign*

Keywords: *corruption, corruption crime, cooperation, conditions, modern methods, foreign experiences, presumption of guilt.*

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan, the formation of a highly organized civil society, in which the mechanisms of self-government are perfectly decided, is defined as a supreme goal. In it, the law is a priority, it contributes to the self-improvement of a person, promotes the realization of the interests of the individual, his rights and freedoms to the fullest extent.

The implementation of such a noble goal provides for the preservation of stability in society, the preservation of peace and tranquility of citizens, the view of people as one of the decisive tasks of ensuring unconditional compliance with laws.

There are many vices that take society to Alexander in different ways. Of these, the most harmful for the state and the people is corruption. This harmful

phenomenon occurs in all countries, regardless of whether they are large and small, wealthy and poor. The term "corruption" comes from the Latin word "corruptio", which means "break" and "buy with bribes". These two words determine the essence of corruption.

In the fight against corruption, first of all, each person must reform his activities. Reforms are primarily a change in human consciousness. The exaltation of anti-corruption enlightenment forms an integral part of this law. The fight against this vice begins primarily with the atmosphere in the family and education-upbringing. What halolu what is forbidden is instilled in our children with the advice of grandparents and momos, parents and teachers.

When the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that "we consider improving the activities of all sections of the education and training system based on the requirements of today as our first-class task", it implies teaching our children from childhood to distinguish pure from unclean and honest from Haram, and speaking about the upbringing of the younger generation, Abdurauf, it is up to them to be happy and to be respected, to be angry or to be despised as weak, to bear the burden of unhappiness, to be

disregarded and subjected to others and to be slaves and captives."

Corruption offenses are a phenomenon that has a serious negative impact on public administration, Community Development and Human negative, and it is a real source that poses a serious threat not only to National, International Security. The observation of the vile being spoken in the bodies of internal affairs causes the existing risk to increase several times.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The current development process of society shows that humanity is increasingly achieving new progress. Humanity, in addition to achieving many achievements in this process, is also carrying in itself some socially negative vices. With the development of humanity, those vices are also developing and demonstrating their new facets. We also include corruption among such socially negative vices. Crimes related to corruption, according to the degree of danger, concern not only law enforcement agencies, but also heads of State. The first president of our country Islam Karimov explained the essence of corruption as follows: "corruption causes irreparable harm to the political and economic path of the country, as well as to the majority of the population. In

addition, during the transition period, when new economic relations are just being founded and a qualitatively different political system is being formed, corruption has the opportunity to block the path of this process by its behavior."

The international nature of corruption is recognized all over the world. This is expressed both in the universality of corruption and in the emergence of transnational types that sharply reduce the effectiveness of its international political, economic and cultural relations. The phenomenon of corruption can be seen in any state. The issues of combating this Vice are becoming increasingly important. Because corruption as a socially dangerous phenomenon directly threatens the stability of state institutions and social life.

professional, fast and effective public service system, to open a wide way for new thinking, enterprising, devoted to El-yurt personnel. We must carry out the concept of Administrative Reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan without deviations in order to fulfill the above mentioned tasks. It is known that in order to effectively fight corruption in our country, a separate law was adopted in this direction. On this basis, a state program is consistently implemented, which includes measures aimed at specific goals. As a result of such work, in 9 months of this year, crimes related to corruption decreased by 33% compared to last year. We are obliged to accept such results as the first effect of our long and long-term activity in the fight against corruption, to carry out more decisive work on this path," we set responsible tasks for the employees of the internal affairs bodies.

On December 22, 2017, in the appeal of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis – "...it is necessary to reform the Institute of Public Service, introduce mechanisms for the effective fight against corruption. Today, life itself requires us to develop an effective system for the formation of a

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the United Nations Convention Against Corruption (New York, October 31, 2003)" of July 7, 2008 became the basis for a new level in the field of improving the legal mechanism for the Prevention of corruption offenses.

Indeed, organized criminal structures that currently have corrupt ties, especially its structures

with international ties and operating internationally, are the most dangerous and complex phenomena that encroach on the national security of Uzbekistan and are inextricably linked with all spheres of social life of society.

It should also be remembered that tamagirlik, torrorny, bribery, arrogance, corruption are extremely infectious and dangerous diseases. If it is not prevented in time, this Maraz can spread throughout the body of society and destroy it. This vice, first of all, puts the person suffering from this disease out of work by eating himself. He honours his faith and the hereafter. Then, it goes on to erode other people, gradually the whole societ.

As mentioned, the existing social risk of corruption offenses makes the fight against it more urgent.

In his essay "open talk about corruption", Christian Lagart, executive director of the International Monetary Fund, reported that the International Monetary Fund, following the results of 2015, estimated the total amount of corruption at 1.5-2 trillion US dollars and bribed 2% of the GDP created in the world. G.Lagart believes that in order to combat corruption, it will be necessary to concentrate the public service with professional and sufficiently independent personnel. As a result of global

surveys conducted, it was known that corruption is a topic that is more discussed by the public than poverty and unemployment.

Corruption is one of the vices that negatively affects the development of any country on Earth. Corruption and bribery are well known from the experience of developed countries in which the state is eroded from the inside. According to the organization Transparency International, which deals with corruption problems, at the moment, more than one trillion dollars a year is appropriated as a result of the scourge of lust, that is, corruption and bribery, which cause many crimes in the world.

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erode other people, gradually the whole society.

There are different opinions on the etymological aspect of the term "corruption". According to supporters of the first widely popular opinion, etymologically the term "corruption" comes from the Latin word "corruptio", which means "deviation in exchange for a bribe".

According to the next view, the term "corruption" comes from the Latin word "corrumpere", which means "violation, nausea, degradation".

According to the third opinion, "corruption" comes from the Latin word "corruptum", which means "broken, broken" and means undermining public interests in the way of personal life and corporate profit.

In some Slavic languages, "corruption" is understood in the meaning of bribes: for example, the section "korrumpirati" in the Serbian-Croatian language translates as "turning to one's side by bribing, bribing", while the quality of "korrupenescu" means "sold, traitor" in the Czech language, corruption in the Russian language is the purchase in exchange for bribes, the Traitor of officials, political figures.

For the first time in international documents, the concept of "corruption" was touched upon in the "code of conduct of officials for the

maintenance of legal order", adopted on December 17, 1979 by the resolution of the UN General Assembly, which states corruption "... it is said that the official, in the interests of the person who gives this award within the framework of his career powers in exchange for a reward of any form, performs or does not perform certain actions without violating or violating the rules of the position guidelines.

In the International Code of Conduct for civil servants, adopted at the 1990 interregional seminar of the UN General Assembly on the problems of "corruption" in Havana, it is said that "corruption is the manifestations of abuse of official duties of officials in the interests of the individual or group, as well as the unlawful use by civil servants of the duties

During the first session of the Council of Europe group on corruption issues in Strasbourg on 22-24 February 1995, it was described that "corruption is the deviation of public or private system officials from bribery in order for them to carry out their duties as part of their career powers."

In the UN Convention Against Corruption, the shortest but most comprehensive definition of corruption is given as follows: "corruption is the abuse of state power for the purpose of personal gain."

In some sources, however, the term is used in addition to words such as "crimes in the field of Economics" and "crimes of officials". When books and articles published in our republic are also called corruption, bribery committed by high officials is implied.

At this point, professor Q.R.Abdurasulova has the following points of view: "corruption is the sum of socially dangerous acts committed by persons performing tasks of State importance and equating to them, using their service powers or opportunities associated with them, for a selfish purpose or other personal interest (responsibility for these acts is provided for by the relevant articles of the JK of the Republic of Uzbekistan)".

Corruption appears in real reality in various forms. The diversity of these images also influences corruption to describe it as a phenomenon or event. For example, Russian scientists S.I. Ozhegov and N.Yu. Shvedova described corruption as a moral violation of officials and politicians. This "moral violation" is manifested in such crimes as the acquisition of illegal wealth, bribery, embezzlement, as well as in the Union of state officials with representatives of criminal elements in the entire system of government.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the fight against corruption" defines "corruption" as the unlawful use of a person's own career or service position in order to obtain material or intangible benefits in the interests of individual persons or other persons, as well as the unlawful provision of such a benefit.

One of the terms that is increasingly used in modern national and international law is corruption. Corruption, of course, is not a vice that appeared today. The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle said about this: "in any state system, through laws and other ordinances, work should be organized in such a way that officials should not be allowed to be enriched in an illegal way." While the French thinker Charles Louis Montesquieu, "...a person with any authority will tend to abuse it, and he will walk in this direction until he achieves a certain goal."

Having studied the issues of the history and development of the origin of corruption, Nicolo Machiavelli compared it to a cough and said: "corruption is also difficult to identify before, like a cough, but it is easy to treat, but it is easy to identify if you miss this patient, but difficult to treat."

American research scientists describe corruption as "a socially dangerous view in the field of politics or public administration." In their opinion, corruption is

manifested by representatives of state power in any form of intentional property and non-property interests and benefits of its service position, as well as in the full acquisition of representatives of this power.

The fight against corruption is one of the most important areas of administrative and legal reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In almost all lectures and speeches of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, special attention is paid to the issues of combating corruption and it is emphasized that it is a barrier to reform and a serious threat to the security of our state.

The totality of the above definitions in relation to corruption is reflected in cases of corruption – violation of legal and moral norms in order to satisfy one's needs and interests at the expense of others.

In other words, corruption is understood as receiving money as a bribe, various goods, types of services, in general, things of different manifestations for personal gain. Corruption is a social phenomenon that threatens the country's economy. This is manifested in bribery. However, "corruption" is a broader concept than "bribery", and bribery forms its basis.

A specific way to combat corruption in Uzbekistan:

This path is to fight by raising the spirituality of a person and

developing the educational sphere. Islam Karmiv's work "High spirituality – the invincible power", published today in dozens of countries around the world, plays an important role in this regard.

This book brings two different life views that are opposite each other, denying each other:

the first is the life views characteristic of people who find their bread behind honest work, who breathe life into the land with impartial and noble deeds, comprehending the meaning of vitality and thinking not only about the pleasures of today's life, but also about the afterlife, about its prosperity;

the second is the thoughts and views of people who, without worrying about the meaning and meaning of life, without tormenting themselves with such questions, succumbed only to the grief of lust and fleeting hoyu amateur, enjoyment and living a light life, completely indifferent to their duty to parents and children, to the country.

Despite the fact that many works have been created on such complex problems, topics as above, the fact that this issue still remains acute and relevant is expressed with concern in the work and wishes to walk people not in the search for Satan, but in the search for mercy.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not

A 1960 law introduced a presumption of corruption guilt against all civil servants in Singapore. This means that when a civil servant applies to expenses that he does not have a salary or owns property, he is considered guilty and involved in the investigation until he proves that his act is legal. At the end of the investigation, when there was not enough evidence to prosecute a civil servant, and at the same time there was some information about his corruption, disciplinary punishment was imposed on him in such a case.

In addition, all officials and their family members were deprived of the right to inviolability. Bureau agents received the right to check not only officials, but also bank accounts belonging to their children, wife, relatives and even friends. Accordingly, if the expenses of the official and his family are higher than the income legally earned, this situation will be enough for the Bureau to start an investigation.

The bureau is usually engaged in the investigation of large bribes in the higher authorities. And against cases of petty bribery, measures were fought to eliminate bureaucracy, simplify decision-making processes, eliminate two different understood norms in laws, allow in areas that are not so

important, and abolish the licensing procedure.

At the same time, the courts were authorized to confiscate income and property acquired in a corrupt way.

The independent bureau fought against bribery even at the highest levels of power.

"Start fighting corruption by sending a friend to jail. You and they are well aware of what the reason is," the prime minister hinted that he would spare no one.

Accordingly, even the closest relatives of Lee Kuan Yun were involved in a corruption investigation. A number of corruption-related officials were sentenced to various terms of imprisonment, or assassinated their lives, or fled the country. Among them was Lee Kuan Yu's dear friend VI Tun bun.

Lee Kuan Yun was not spared by his close friend, VI Tun bun, who held the position of Minister.

"VI Tun bun served as Minister of the environment in 1975 when he went on a trip to Indonesia with his family. And the travel money was paid by the contractor organization that was building housing. He receives as a bribe a mansion from this contractor worth 500 thousand Singapore dollars, and also draws up two loans worth 300 thousand dollars in the name of his father on the basis of the contractor's guarantee. The goal

was to use this money for speculation purposes in the stock market.

VI Tun bun has been a loyal non-communist leader since the 1950s, so it has been hard for me to defend him and hear his unreliable attempts on the subject of his innocence. He was found guilty and sentenced to 4 years and 6 months in prison. Despite complaining about the sentence, he was left in power, although the prison term was reduced to 18 months," Lee Kuan Yu recalls in his memoirs.

By the way, personally Lee Kuan Yu and his family members were also repeatedly checked by the Bureau, but the investigations did not reveal the Prime Minister's involvement in corruption.

Currently, Singapore is in the leading positions in the world in terms of the low scale of corruption, the level of economic freedom and development.

In particular, in the ranking published by Transparency International for 2020, Singapore ranked 3rd among the lowest corruption countries.

With only 4 million inhabitants, Singapore's experience has demonstrated that corruption can be reduced to a very low level in a few decades in exchange for political will, effective anti-corruption legislation, and an independent agency that cannot be sold for money.

So it would be better to prefer the rule of law than anything else, to promote and adhere to the principle of equality of all in society before the law, while eliminating corruption by sparing even high-ranking officials and relatives along the way.

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